

INTERPRETATION OF IMAGE AND CHARACTERS IN THE NOVEL "THE LAST STATION"

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Abstract. *Shukur Kholmirzaev will criticize as a unique personal style owner, a sanity, avoid statements. Although it is steadfast, it is achieved only full and bright to the student. However, sometimes his works are impressed as unfinished. The judgment against the heroes of the game will be brought to the attention of the reader. The article in this article studied art skills in the novel " The Last Station " of the writer Shukur Kholmirzaev.*

Keywords: *artistic image, artistic intention, creative process, language of the work, work, national traditions, real person, artistic texture, writer's fantasy, inner world of the hero, artistry, artistic skill, individual style, artistic visual tools, character, hero ma spiritual world.*

INTRODUCTION

Shukur Kholmirzayev is one of the well-known writers who made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature of the 20th century. He has a special place in the spiritual growth of the Uzbek people through his unique prose created with high artistic skill.

Since artistry is both the soul and the soul of art, one of the main means of creating it is the artistic image, and it is considered the central problem of the science of literary studies.

Because in the science of literary studies, "image" means not only the events perceived in the human mind, but also the life realized, reworked (interwoven) and depicted by the artist through the medium of words. "... There is nothing random or superfluous in it. All parts are subordinate to the whole, all are directed to one goal, all together bring forth one beauty, integrity, individuality. [2, 101].

Art's thinking through images is its specific, i.e., defining characteristic as a species. An artist perceives the world by means of an artistic image, expresses the essence he perceives and his emotional attitude to what he perceives. In this sense, the image is considered a form of thinking, a method of literature and art; The way of thinking typical of literature and art is called "figurative thinking" because it thinks through images.

As the writer himself said, the characters of each of his works, whether they are positive or negative, try to approach him as much as possible in a positive and negative way. It is no exaggeration to say that Adib's novel " The Last Station " is one of those works.

Shukur Kholmirzayev was able to express his longings through images in his first novel "The Last Station" with great courage. In 1976, the novel was published in issues 3-5 of the "Eastern Star" magazine, and soon after it was published as a book. It has been more than fifty years since the novel reached the hands of readers and became their spiritual property. A chance for a young man to become middle-aged.

Shukur Kholmirzayev writes in the preface: "The story of the novel takes place in the village of Bekat. Then, in the lives of the heroes of the work, there are destinations that have been reached or not reached, which I would also like to call "stations". Besides, this is my stop in creativity and research. So, the name "station" is symbolic. [5, 3].

The basis of literature, the factor that brings it into the world is life. Since it is capable of inexhaustible creative power, renewal, growth and development, literature also embodies this ability, it also does not stop progressing towards perfection, discovering innovations that give life. Of course, literature fulfills this task by studying and researching the interaction of the human spirit with spirituality and social existence. Because it is impossible to imagine social existence without spirituality, humanity without social existence.

Spirituality (also has the meaning of a person's inner spiritual life) is a barometer of a person's soul and spirit in a broad sense; He is a teacher who brings together knowledge, skills and experiences in moral, economic, political, social, cultural, ideological, legal, religious, technical, educational, philosophical and similar fields and leads to purity. Spirituality is when a person achieves the purity of his heart through his activities and knows his identity. Where the root of spirituality - faith, belief, trust and conscience is not clean - spirituality prevails [4, 23].

The work begins with the following image: "Even though the Afghan wind died down yesterday, it still hasn't cooled down, the express bus crunching on the asphalt in the sand was cold inside, and the windows were cold." Most of the people on the bus were people of the desert, so it seems that they don't know much about the heat, but the heat made the two people very restless.

They are a couple. Munira with Sadiq. They are sitting behind. In the morning, they got on the bus later, and got this place.

Sadiq is a chubby young man with coarse hair as if smeared with black oil. He is sitting sullenly; he even looks uncomfortable. Munira is three years younger than her husband, at twenty-eight. He is also full, but he is young with tonsils. A person who takes a close look at his face will feel something special and think that he must be a person from another country [5, 5].

Vivid scenes of life in "The Last Station" will fascinate the reader, - says literary scholar M. Koshjanov in the book "Selection". - "The characters created by Shukur Kholmiraev in the novel are not people who are satisfied only with gaining personal freedom. At the same time, they think about the interests of the whole society, they understand well that in order to ensure the development of the society, it is necessary to preserve the cultural heritage that has reached us from the past. [3, 199].

According to the literary scholar, each of the heroes of the novel has its own characteristics, and with these characteristics, this fate, these fates, we do not notice the writer's attitude to the real characters and their behavior. Thus, some of their characteristics, in some places, the fate of entire situations, even characters, becomes uncertain," says the critic. The scientist believes that the source of flaws in the novel lies in the impartiality of the writer's style. The critic emphasizes that there are many characters, episodes, and situations in the novel that are poorly explained and given little meaning, and that these situations cannot be forgiven.

"The Last Station" made a radical change not only in literary works, but also in our prose. With his work of experimentation, the writer broke the rigid literary and stylistic patterns and had a significant impact on the development of national thought. The importance of the work in the growth of the literary and artistic taste of the readers was great. Novel art was read with interest and debated because it is close to the heart and soul of people and people. In general, in the novel, there is no praise for the honor of the collective farm activist, collectivization advocate, farmer, which the lovers of literature of that time were forced to get used to.

The name "Last Stop" is symbolic, as noted by the writer. As a person is condemned to various trials and difficulties, happiness and unhappiness, happy and sad days during his life, as

his life consists of different stages and stations, while he is growing and developing in the process of moving from this station to this station, literature, a true writer must describe these same processes with great care and skill. The writer acted according to these. That is, it reflected only one stop in the life of the characters of the novel. If we take into account that life goes on, it will have new demands and wishes, we realize that the writer did not intervene in the fate of the heroes in vain, did not make a subjective judgment about them, and did not leave the final conclusion to the reader in vain.

The novel contains the image of people searching for their identity. The spiritual and social life of the society is truthfully reflected in the work. With the novel "Last Stop", the writer rejects the literary standards and standards of his time, norms and standards. He wants to prove that the literary work is different from publicism and journalistic research, and that the writer should study the human heart. The reason is that the period when the novel was written and published was the reigning period of socialist realism. It was impossible to doubt this path.

The heroes of the novel are mostly young people. At the time when the novel was written, the writer himself was not yet thirty-five. He consciously chose the life of his peers for the work. Therefore, it is obvious that the novel was written in an enthusiastic mood, with passion, and it evokes such a mood. The novel is written in a very simple and simple way. The language is smooth and juicy.

The events of the novel take place in Bekat - a space that combines old and new without false pathos and artificial noises. The writer impartially describes this life and the events in it. The images and characters in the work are clearly drawn. Everyone has their own image, world.

Even if we read the novel with the eyes of today, we will feel satisfaction and satisfaction. Because the idea is eternal and immortal. The light and shine that gives beauty to the work is also in its essence. If some places in the novel - scenes related to farm life and words and concepts representing the politics of the time are edited - a wonderful national-psychological work will appear. There is no hero in the novel who surprises the reader and performs miracles. The characters and characters created are ordinary people. But they have other "problems" other than everyday worries and household problems, which is why their rank is high. For this reason, their fate makes the reader think, leads to different thoughts and imaginations. The novel also shows great socio-spiritual tragedies, but there is no explanation for it either from the language of the hero or from the language of the writer. The reader will understand. The family of Sadiq and Munira, the heroes of the play, is a deposit. For old man Barot, family is not worth a dime. Old man Ishak is half a man. After killing the old woman, she leaned on her daughter-in-law. The family, built by his son Mamarajab and his daughter-in-law Nasiba, was born without a building. Uktam, the head of the household, does not consider himself guilty of the fact that this young family is falling apart. Ahadova, a teacher, lives alone in Termez because her husband is a soldier. Three sons in three cities. Her womanly dream is to have a whole family. As we mentioned above, at first glance, the family crisis and disorganization, which are the backbone of the society, are not obvious. But in the socialist system, it is possible to see that families have come to the edge of a precipice. This episode and the situation of characters in the novel will not leave the reader indifferent. The reader sympathizes with one of them, and does not hide his hatred for the other. Because the novel confronts us with a vital, real person: we don't see a made-up, polished image. In general, each character in the work has its own role.

"The reason why we consider character creation to be the core issue of art is that character includes many elements of artistic creation (such as plot, composition, language), or rather forces it to "work". That is, if the character is a form in relation to the content of the work, then the plot, composition, language (all tricks of the style) are in relation to the character. As Izzat Sultan, a literary scholar, noted, "The content of the work acquires life clarity due to the character description, and at the same time, it has the ability to affect our feelings." [7, 5-6].

As we mentioned above, each character in the novel "Last Station" is approached in a unique way. When creating an image, imagination and a conscious attitude to the material are always necessary.

Where only attention is paid to the imagination, there one aspect of creativity becomes especially expensive and generally does not satisfy the taste of generations. Only when both sides have equal principles - the right path will be found. That's why Schiller says, "Imagination, combined with reason, produces a poet-artist." Yes, the imagination acquires truth only with the participation of the mind.

"Every writer is a critic for himself," writes People's Writer of Uzbekistan Pirmkul Kadyrov in the book "Thoughts". , accepts each work based on the needs of the reader, the demands of literature and the intentions of the author's heart. [4, 38]. So, one of the laws of artistic creation correctly shows the fact that the author should objectify not only his created work, but also himself. We can observe the phenomenon of creation and control at the same time in the novel "The Last Station".

At first glance, it seems that the heroes of the work have two different faces. At first, the reader gets such an impression after seeing some of the deeds and vices of people who love their country, who dream of returning to their originality, who live with big ideas. This situation often does not correspond to the conclusions drawn in traditional works that this is a negative character, this is a positive character, this is white, this is black. The writer who expertly uses every detail and assigns universal meaning to it uses this contradiction to thicken the symbolism characteristic of the general spirit of the work.

This work can be called a national-psychological work. Because in the image of people who cherish and promote Uzbek clans, history, traditions and rituals of Uzbekistan, the writer intended to embody the image of the entire Uzbek people and achieved this. This idea, embedded in the spirit of the work, was pursued in its time. The writer, who aimed to achieve national awakening in the hearts of people during the strict regime, committed to this good work long ago and was able to achieve it.

In the novel, the writer tries to show the problems of the time in which he lives, especially the fact that the nation is losing its identity, disconnected from its past, and losing everything through symbols.

One of the heroes of the novel, Guvvatbekov, although he lives with the dream of going to Tashkent, stays in Bekat and leads educational work, Munira also stays in Bekat, settles in the school named after Mahmud Kashgari as a history teacher, and reveals the secret of Ajinatepa. there is a symbolic reference to the realization of the great goal of getting young people to know their identity through education, historical consciousness, and historical memory. We can even see the realization of the goal of returning to one's identity in the performance of the griya, which is an ancient folk song of the mountain people, which is forgotten today, and recorded by his student Boybori at Sabohat's funeral. Oktam's breakup with Nasiba, after long hesitation, he destroys the

old garden and starts to build a new one, Shamshiddinov, who has been taking people's money and treating his body until then, realizes that after a short conversation with Munira, he needs a salve for the human psyche, and now cases such as the decision to treat with beds for free can be evaluated not only as "awakening of conscience and humanity prevailed in their spirituality", but as the nation's turning to enlightenment, restoration of its historical memory. It is closer to the truth that Ishaq Baba's courage and faith in old Barot are viewed as distrust of those mentioned above. Nasiba's transformation into a different person, which is expressed through a stranger's look at Oktam, and Sadiq's escape from Bekat also have symbolic meanings. At the end of the work, the changes that took place in Bekat - the retreat of evil and the predominance of goodness - were highlighted by the author in a unique way.

CONCLUSION

In general, this novel of Shukur Kholmiraev, among other works, is among the works that have come to the reader's attention. Because today the attitude towards his works and heroes has not changed. He treats each of his heroes with his own love and respect. This is also evident in the description of his appearance and mentality. In order to clearly show the nature of this hero, he uses landscapes alternately. He pays special attention not only to landscapes, but also to the construction of monologues and dialogues. That is why the image and mentality of the heroes have a special place in his works.

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